

Real-time Attack Simulation and Detection Using WAZUH and Telegram Alerts

By: Chrisna Dhefanni, Martin Suhartana

A. TOPOLOGY

Figure 1 Traffic Flow

Traffic flow on Figure 1 above has a detailed following explanation:

- **Green** illustrates connection flow from user segment to DMZ segment which includes user access to the web application located in the DMZ segment.
- **Blue** illustrates connection flow from web server segment that accesses the database server to manage data needed by the web application.
- **Pink** illustrates connection flow of log data sent by Wazuh agent installed on the web server to the Wazuh server for analysis.
- **Purple** illustrates connection flow from Wazuh server to Telegram server on the internet to send notifications related to threat detection.

B. IMPLEMENTATION ENVIRONMENT

1. VIRTUAL DEVICES LIST

List of virtual devices that has been used in this simulation are shown in Table 1 below:

Table 1 Virtual Devices

No	Hostname	Description
1	core-switch	The core switch serves as the main regulator of data traffic in the simulation.
2	gw-user	The gateway router in the user segment acts as a gateway that organizes and directs data traffic in and out of the user segment network.
3	gw-mgmt	The gateway router in the management segment acts as a gateway that manages and directs data traffic in and out of the management segment network.
4	gw-dmz	The gateway router in the DMZ segment acts as a gateway that manages and directs data traffic in and out of the DMZ segment network.
5	gw-sf	The gateway router on the server farm segment acts as a gateway that manages and directs data traffic in and out of the server farm segment network.
6	user-01	Users are individual entities or devices that access the network to utilize the resources or services provided, such as web applications.
7	attacker-01	Attacker is a party that seeks to exploit vulnerabilities in network systems with the aim of gaining unauthorized access, stealing information, or causing disruption to services.
8	Admin-01	An administrator is an individual who is responsible for the management and maintenance of the network, which includes configuration, monitoring.
9	web-server-01	A web server is a computer that functions to store and serve web pages to users via the HTTP protocol.

10	wazuh-server	Wazuh server is the main component in this research. The Wazuh server is responsible for threat detection, data correlation, and generating alerts based on predefined rules.
11	db-server	A database server is a computer that stores and manages data for applications that require it.
12	sw-acc-user	User segment accessswitch a network device that connects various devices in a user segment.
13	sw-acc-sf	A server farm segment access switch is a network device that connects various devices in a server farm segment.

2. IP ADDRESSES ALLOCATION

List of IP address that has been allocated in this simulation are shown in Table 2 below:

Table 2 IP Addresses Allocation

No	Hostname	IP Address
1	core-switch	10.10.10.1/30 10.10.10.5/30 10.10.10.9/30 10.10.10.13/30
2	gw-user	10.10.10.2/30 192.168.1.1/24
3	gw-mgmt	10.10.10.14/30 172.16.0.1/24
4	gw-dmz	10.10.10.10/30 172.16.32.1/24
5	gw-sf	10.10.10.5/30 10.10.20.1/24
6	user-01	192.168.1.3/24
7	attacker-01	192.168.1.3/24
8	Admin-01	172.16.0.2/24
9	web-server-01	172.16.32.2/24
10	wazuh-server	10.10.20.2/24
11	db-server	10.10.20.3/24

3. DEVICE SPECIFICATION AND CONFIGURATION

List of devices specification and configuration that has been used in this simulation are shown in Table 3 below:

Table 3 Device Specification and Configuration

No	Hostname	Specifications	Configuration
1	core-switch	OS: Cisco IOL L3 CPU:1 RAM: 1Gb DISK: 1Gb	Routing: 0.0.0.0/0 via <ip host> 192.168.1.0/24 via 10.10.10.2 172.16.0.0/24 via 10.10.10.14 172.16.32.0/24 via 10.10.10.10 10.10.20.0/24 via 10.10.10.6
2	gw-user	OS: Cisco IOL L3 CPU:1 RAM: 1Gb DISK: 1Gb	Routing: 172.16.32.0/24 via 10.10.10.1
3	gw-mgmt	OS: Cisco IOL L3 CPU:1 RAM: 1Gb DISK: 1Gb	Routing: 172.16.32.0/24 via 10.10.10.13 10.10.20.0/24 via 10.10.10.13
4	gw-dmz	OS: Cisco IOL L3 CPU:1 RAM: 1Gb DISK: 1Gb	Routing: 0.0.0.0/0 via 10.10.10.9
5	gw-sf	OS Cisco IOL L3 CPU:1 RAM: 1Gb DISK: 1Gb	Routing: 0.0.0.0/0 via 10.10.10.5 172.16.32.0/24 via 10.10.10.5

			172.16.0.0/24 via 10.10.10.5
			Access lits: Deny to 192.168.1.0/24 Allow to any
6	user-01	OS:Ubuntu Desktop 24.04 CPU: 2 RAM: 4Gb Disk: 50Gb	Routing: 0.0.0.0/0 via 192.168.1.1 Installed applications: Web browser
7	attacker-01	OS: Kali Linux 2024.04 CPU: 2 RAM: 6Gb Disk: 50Gb	Routing: 0.0.0.0/0 via 192.168.1.1 Installed applications: Web browser, dan slowhttptest
8	Admin-01	OS: Ubuntu Desktop 24.04 CPU: 2 RAM: 4Gb Disk: 50Gb	Routing: 0.0.0.0/0 via 172.16.0.1 Installed applications: Web browser
9	web-server-01	OS: Ubuntu Server 22.04 CPU: 2 RAM: 4Gb Disk: 50Gb	Routing: 0.0.0.0/0 via 172.16.32.1 Installed applications: Apache2, mariadb-client, php, php-mysql, php-gd, libapache2-mod-php, git, DVWA, dan wazuh-agent Policy wazuh agent: forwading log Apache2

10	wazuh-server	OS: Ubuntu Server 22.04 CPU: 2 RAM: 4Gb Disk: 50Gb	Routing: 0.0.0.0/0 via 10.10.20.1 Installed applications: Wazuh server, integrasi notifikasi Telegram
11	db-server	OS: Ubuntu Server 22.04 CPU: 2 RAM: 4Gb Disk: 50Gb	Routing: 0.0.0.0/0 via 10.10.20.1 Installed applications: mariadb-server mariadb- client
12	sw-acc-user	OS: Cisco IOL I2 CPU:1 RAM: 1Gb DISK: 1Gb	-
13	sw-acc-sf	OS: Cisco IOL I2 CPU:1 RAM: 1Gb DISK: 1Gb	-